

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THE CLASSROOM MANAGEMENT TECHNIQUES OF TEACHERS AND THEIR HAPPINESS INDEX: BASIS OF AN INTEGRATED FACULTY DEVELOPMENT PROGRAM

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the relationship between classroom management techniques and the happiness index of private high school teachers in Northern Luzon, Philippines. Specifically, it examined the extent to which Positive Behavioral, Punitive Disciplinary, and Social-Emotional Learning (SEL) techniques were utilized, how these approaches related to teachers' perceived happiness, and the key classroom management challenges, while also proposing an integrated faculty development program. An embedded mixed methods design was employed, involving 43 teachers from two private secondary schools. Quantitative data were collected through structured surveys assessing classroom management practices and happiness index levels, and were analyzed using descriptive statistics and correlation analysis. Qualitative data from open-ended responses were examined through thematic analysis to identify recurring classroom challenges. Findings revealed that teachers utilized SEL and positive behavioral techniques at very high levels, whereas punitive disciplinary techniques were moderately applied. Teachers reported a very high level of workplace happiness, although satisfaction with pay was relatively low. Significant positive correlations were found between happiness index and both positive behavioral and SEL techniques, while punitive disciplinary techniques showed no meaningful relationship with happiness index. Managing student behavior emerged as the primary classroom challenge, followed by concerns related to student motivation, overcrowding, time management, and instructional diversity. The study concludes that supportive and relationship-centered classroom management practices significantly enhance teacher happiness, underscoring the importance of sustained professional development and institutional support systems to promote teacher well-being and effective classroom environments.

Keywords: *classroom management techniques, happiness index, positive behavioral, punitive disciplinary, social-emotional learning, classroom management challenges*

INTRODUCTION

The development of healthy and thriving societies depends largely on the cultivation of psychologically well and professionally fulfilled teachers. Recognizing this, President Ferdinand R. Marcos Jr. signed into law the Republic Act No. 12080, also known as the “Basic Education Mental Health and Well-Being Promotion Act,” on December 6, 2024 (Official Gazette of the Philippines, 2024), institutionalizing mental health and well-being programs for learners and school personnel in both public and private basic education institutions. This policy development underscores the timeliness of examining teacher well-being not merely as an individual concern but as a national educational priority.

Within schools, teachers serve as primary agents in fostering students’ academic growth and emotional development. Consequently, their well-being directly influences classroom climate, instructional quality, and student engagement. In the two private secondary schools in Nueva Vizcaya, where this study was conducted, teachers consistently report for duty; however, they commonly handle 20–30 teaching hours per week. Although higher teaching loads may correspond to increased compensation in private schools, prolonged instructional hours may affect lesson preparation, classroom management, emotional regulation, and work-life balance, key domains reflected in the happiness index (Kumar et al., 2024; Zheng, 2022).

Teacher happiness, defined as the sense of fulfillment and professional worth derived from teaching (Zheng, 2022), extends beyond the absence of burnout and captures holistic well-being, life satisfaction, and flourishing (Kumar et al., 2024). While existing research highlights stress, workload pressures, and insufficient policy support as threats to teacher well-being (Tham et al., 2022; Dahiya & Malik, 2024), limited attention has been given to structured measures of teacher happiness in Northern Luzon, particularly within private secondary schools. Most local studies emphasize organizational climate or job satisfaction, leaving emotional well-being and daily classroom experiences underexplored.

Moreover, few studies in the region investigate how specific classroom management techniques, positive behavioral, punitive disciplinary, and social-emotional learning (SEL), relate to teachers’ happiness. Despite short-term wellness initiatives in participating schools, sustained monitoring and systematic follow-through remain limited. This contextual, regional, and institutional gap establishes the rationale for the present study. Thus, this research examined the relationship between private secondary school teachers’ classroom management techniques and their happiness index and identified classroom management challenges, providing localized evidence to inform policy decisions, administrative strategies, and sustainable teacher wellness programs in the Cagayan Valley region.

Review of Related Literature

Classroom Management Techniques

Classroom management significantly shapes instructional effectiveness and classroom climate. Bear et al. (2021) categorized classroom management into three primary techniques: positive behavioral, punitive disciplinary, and social-emotional learning (SEL). This framework provides a conceptual structure for analyzing contemporary research. Despite extensive international literature, no published study in Nueva Vizcaya, specifically examines how private secondary school teachers apply these techniques, creating a contextual gap in localized evidence.

Positive Behavioral Techniques

Positive Behavioral Techniques emphasize reinforcement, praise, proactive planning, and structured support. Studies indicate that proactive teachers who consistently apply reinforcement achieve improved classroom outcomes (Clark et al., 2023; Baker, 2022). Teacher emotions also play a mediating role; positive emotions such as enjoyment predict higher teaching quality, while anger and anxiety correlate negatively with classroom effectiveness (Burić & Frenzel, 2023; Frenzel et al., 2021). Although international findings affirm the effectiveness of positive behavioral approaches, their implementation within private school contexts in Northern Luzon remains insufficiently examined.

Punitive Disciplinary Techniques

Punitive Disciplinary Techniques rely on reprimands, removal, and reactive discipline. Research associates such methods with a weaker classroom climate and lower teacher self-efficacy (Bolat, 2023; Burić et al., 2020). School-wide positive behavior frameworks demonstrate lower suspension rates compared to exclusionary discipline (Grasley-Boy et al., 2021). While punitive measures may yield short-term compliance, literature suggests potential long-term emotional and relational costs. However, limited localized data explore how administrative expectations in private schools influence reliance on such strategies.

Social-Emotional Learning (SEL) Techniques

Social-Emotional Learning Techniques integrate emotional regulation, empathy, and relationship-building into classroom management. Supportive teacher profiles demonstrate stronger classroom regulation and lower stress levels (Jiang et al., 2024). Meta-analytic evidence confirms that SEL improves student behavior, relationships, and academic achievement (Cipriano et al., 2023). Reciprocal relationships between teacher-student rapport and student emotions further validate SEL's developmental impact (Goetz et al., 2021). Despite global support, localized studies determining the consistency of SEL implementation in private secondary schools are lacking.

Happiness Index of Teachers

Teacher happiness is multidimensional, shaped by psychological, organizational, and societal factors. Studies identify themes such as work-life balance, resilience, commitment, and motivation as integral components of teacher well-being (Magtubo & Dela Cerna, 2023). Organizational commitment and institutional support significantly predict school happiness (Bahat & Isik, 2023), while positive affect and self-efficacy mediate classroom relationships (Lin et al., 2022). International comparisons demonstrate how policy and societal respect influence teacher well-being, as seen in Finland (Sharma, 2025) and selected U.S. states (Treleaven, 2024).

Although national and global research affirms the importance of teacher happiness, no published study in Nueva Vizcaya examines the happiness index of private secondary school teachers in relation to classroom management techniques. Most research centers on public institutions or broad national samples, overlooking the unique workload structures, governance models, and compensation systems in private schools.

Classroom Management Challenges

Teachers encounter recurring classroom management challenges, including disruptive behaviors, resource limitations, overcrowding, technological distractions, and policy constraints (Arisandi et al., 2022; Bano et al., 2025; Goldman, 2024). Quantitative evidence indicates that well-managed classrooms yield significantly more instructional time (Irwin et al., 2024). Philippine-based studies further highlight contextual difficulties such as multi-grade teaching demands and systemic resource shortages (Marfe, 2024; Alarcon et al., 2024; MadamDama, 2023).

While these studies document behavioral, institutional, and socio-economic barriers, few examine how such challenges intersect with teachers' happiness, particularly within private secondary schools in Northern Luzon.

The reviewed literature consistently demonstrates that classroom management techniques influence classroom climate, teacher emotions, and student outcomes, while teacher happiness is shaped by psychological resilience, institutional support, and broader policy contexts. However, a critical gap exists in localized research integrating these two domains, classroom management and teacher happiness, within private secondary schools in Nueva Vizcaya.

Given the recent national emphasis on mental health policy, evolving classroom demands, and the limited duration of existing wellness initiatives in private schools, this study addresses a timely and context-specific need. By examining the relationship between classroom management techniques and teachers' happiness index, this research contributes empirical evidence to guide administrators, policymakers, and educators in designing sustained, data-driven interventions that promote both effective classroom practice and long-term teacher well-being.

Research Questions

The study sought to determine the relationship between teachers' classroom management techniques and their happiness index. The findings served as the basis of a proposed program. Specifically, the study sought answers to the following questions:

1. What are the Classroom Management Techniques of the teachers in terms of
 - 1.1. Positive Behavioral Techniques
 - 1.2. Punitive Disciplinary Techniques
 - 1.3. Social-Emotional Learning Techniques?
2. How do teachers perceive their level of happiness index?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the classroom management techniques of teachers and their happiness index?
4. What are the primary challenges encountered by the teachers relative to classroom management?
5. Based on the findings of the study, what integrated faculty development program may be proposed?

METHODOLOGY

This study employed an embedded mixed-methods research design to examine the relationship between teachers' classroom management techniques and their happiness index then understand the challenges teachers encounter in classroom management. An embedded mixed-methods design integrates both quantitative and qualitative approaches within a single study, where one form of data supports the other to provide a deeper understanding of the research problem (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2018).

The study was conducted in two private secondary schools located in Nueva Vizcaya, Philippines. The study utilized total population sampling, a form of purposive sampling where all members of a defined population who meet the inclusion criteria are selected as respondents (Etikan & Bala, 2017). A total of forty-three (43) high school teachers participated in the study, representing the entire teaching population of the selected institutions during the conduct of the research. The respondents were required to have at least one year of teaching experience to ensure that they had sufficient exposure to classroom management situations.

The research instrument consisted of two validated questionnaires and a set of open-ended questions. The first instrument was the Delaware Positive Behavioral, Punitive Disciplinary, and Social-Emotional Learning Techniques Scale (DTS) developed by Bear et al. (2021), which includes 16 items divided into three subscales: Positive Behavioral Techniques, Punitive Disciplinary Techniques, and Social-Emotional Learning Techniques. The second instrument was the Happiness at Work (HAW) Scale developed by Salas-Vallina and Vidal (2018), which contains 9 items measuring engagement, job satisfaction, and affective organizational commitment. Both instruments utilized a 4-point Likert scale to measure responses. The reliability and validity of these instruments were

previously established by their respective authors. In addition, two open-ended questions were included to gather qualitative data regarding the classroom management challenges experienced by teachers. Prior to data collection, permission to use the instruments was secured from the original authors. Data were collected through an online survey using Google Forms during the second semester of School Year 2024–2025.

The data gathered were analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistical tools. The mean and standard deviation were used to determine the level of teachers' classroom management techniques and their happiness index. To examine the relationship between classroom management techniques and the happiness index, the Pearson Product–Moment Correlation Coefficient (Pearson r) was used to determine the strength and direction of the relationship between variables, while Multiple Linear Regression Analysis was employed to identify the predictive influence of the different classroom management techniques on teachers' happiness. For the qualitative data, thematic analysis was used to identify recurring patterns and themes related to the classroom management challenges experienced by teachers. The responses were carefully reviewed, coded, and grouped into themes.

RESULTS

1. Classroom Management Techniques of the Teachers in terms of:

1.1 Positive Behavioral Techniques

Table 1
Classroom Management Techniques of the Teachers
in terms of Positive Behavioral

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
Students are praised often.	3.16	0.615	High
Students are often given rewards for being good.	3.30	0.599	Very High
Teachers often let students know when they are being good.	3.53	0.550	Very High
Classes get rewards for good behavior.	3.40	0.495	Very High
Teachers use just enough praise and rewards; not too much or too little.	3.07	0.669	High
Overall Level of Positive Behavioral Techniques	3.29	0.363	Very High

Legend: Low (1.00-1.75), Moderate (1.76-2.51), High (2.52-3.27), Very High (3.28-4.00)

Table 1 outlines the extent to which teachers employ positive behavior techniques in classroom management. The overall mean score is 3.29 (SD = 0.363), which falls within the “Very High” category. Three out of five individual indicators were also rated as “Very High,” with mean scores ranging from 3.30 to 3.53. The highest-rated item is “Teachers often let students know when they are being good” (M = 3.53, SD = 0.550), followed closely by other indicators related to giving rewards and praising students. The lowest indicator rated as “High” is “Teachers use just enough praise and rewards; not too much

or too little” (M = 3.07, SD = 0.669). Notably, this indicator did not reach the “Very High” level, revealing a subtle difference between frequent use of praise and the careful regulation of its amount and timing.

1.2 Punitive Disciplinary Techniques

Table 2
Classroom Management Techniques of the Teachers
in terms of Punitive Disciplinary

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
Students are punished a lot.	1.79	0.675	Moderate
Students are often sent out of class for breaking rules.	1.79	0.742	Moderate
Students are often yelled at by adults.	1.98	0.597	Moderate
Many students are sent to the office for breaking rules.	2.44	0.765	Moderate
Students are punished too much for minor things.	1.67	0.522	Low
Overall Level of Punitive Disciplinary Techniques	1.93	0.447	Moderate

Legend: Low (1.00-1.75), Moderate (1.76-2.51), High (2.52-3.27), Very High (3.28-4.00)

Table 2 shows the extent to which teachers use punitive disciplinary techniques in classroom management. The overall mean score is 1.93 (SD = 0.447), which falls within the “Moderate” category. Most individual indicators are also rated as “Moderate,” with mean scores ranging from 1.79 to 2.44. The highest-rated item is “Many students are sent to the office for breaking rules” (M = 2.44, SD = 0.765), indicating that this action is occasionally employed. Meanwhile, the lowest-rated item is “Students are punished too much for minor things” (M = 1.67, SD = 0.522), which is interpreted as “Low,” suggesting restraint in administering excessive discipline for minor infractions. This item is the only indicator classified as “Low,” highlighting teachers’ effort to avoid disproportionate responses to minor misbehavior.

1.3 Social-Emotional Learning Techniques

Table 3
Classroom Management Techniques of the Teachers
in terms of Social-Emotional Learning

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
Students are taught to feel responsible for how they act.	3.42	0.663	Very High
Students are taught to understand how others think and feel.	3.65	0.529	Very High
Students are taught that they can control their own behavior.	3.47	0.550	Very High
Students are taught how to solve conflicts with others.	3.51	0.551	Very High
Students are taught they should care about how others feel.	3.60	0.541	Very High
Students are often asked to help decide what is best for the class or school.	3.56	0.502	Very High

Overall Level of Social-Emotional Learning Techniques 3.53 0.404 Very High

Legend: Low (1.00-1.75), Moderate (1.76-2.51), High (2.52-3.27), Very High (3.28-4.00)

Table 3 presents the extent to which teachers implement social-emotional learning (SEL) techniques in classroom management. The results show an overall mean score of 3.53 (SD = 0.404), categorized as “Very High.” The highest-rated item is “Students are taught to understand how others think and feel” (M = 3.65, SD = 0.529), while the lowest-rated item is “Students are taught to feel responsible for how they act” (M = 3.42, SD = 0.663). Other indicators, including teaching self-control, empathy, conflict resolution, and participatory decision-making, also received consistently high ratings.

Although all indicators fall within the “Very High” range, the comparatively lower mean for personal responsibility (M = 3.42) indicates a slight divergence in emphasis, suggesting that accountability-building practices may not be as strongly reinforced as perspective-taking and empathy. Moreover, this item recorded the highest variability (SD = 0.663), indicating differences in how consistently teachers cultivate students’ sense of responsibility across classrooms.

2. Perceived Level of Happiness at Work of Teachers

**Table 4
Perceived Level of Happiness at Work of Teachers**

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
At my job, I feel strong and vigorous.	3.16	0.615	High
I am enthusiastic about my job.	3.30	0.599	Very High
I get carried away when I am working. [R]	3.53	0.550	Very High
I am satisfied with the nature of the work I perform.	3.40	0.495	Very High
I am satisfied with the pay I receive for my job.	3.07	0.669	High
I am satisfied with the opportunities that exist in this organization for advancement [promotion].	3.29	0.363	Very High
I would be very happy to spend the rest of my career with this organization.	3.16	0.615	High
I feel emotionally attached to this organization.	3.30	0.599	Very High
I feel a strong sense of belonging to my organization.	3.53	0.550	Very High
Overall Happiness Index	3.40	0.495	Very High

Legend: Low (1.00-1.75), Moderate (1.76-2.51), High (2.52-3.27), Very High (3.28-4.00)

Table 4 presents the perceived level of happiness at work among teachers across various indicators. The results reveal an overall mean score of 3.40 (SD = 0.495), interpreted as “Very High,” indicating that teachers generally experience a high degree of positive emotion and satisfaction in their workplace.

The highest-rated indicators are “I get carried away when I am working [R]” and “I feel a strong sense of belonging to my organization,” both with a mean score of 3.53 (SD =

0.550), interpreted as Very High. In contrast, the lowest-rated item is “I am satisfied with the pay I receive for my job” (M = 3.07, SD = 0.669), which falls within the “High” category. Although still positively rated, this indicator reflects the lowest evaluation among all items, suggesting a gap between intrinsic satisfaction and extrinsic compensation. The relatively higher standard deviation (SD = 0.669) also indicates greater variability in teachers’ perceptions of salary satisfaction compared with other indicators of workplace happiness.

3. Correlation Between the Classroom Management Styles of Teachers and their Happiness Index

Table 5
Pearson Correlation Between the Classroom Management Techniques of teachers and their Happiness Index

Classroom Management Techniques	<i>r</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>p</i>	Significance	Inference
Positive Behavioral	0.447**	41	0.003	Significant	Reject H ₀
Punitive Disciplinary	-0.166	41	0.288	Significant	Retain H ₀
Social-Emotional Learning	0.368*	41	0.015	Not Significant	Reject H ₀

Note. * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$

Table 5 presents the Pearson correlation analysis examining the relationship between teachers’ classroom management techniques and their happiness index. The results reveal a moderately positive and statistically significant correlation between the Positive Behavioral Technique and the happiness index ($r = 0.447$, $p = 0.003$), leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis (H_0). Similarly, the Social Emotional Learning (SEL) Techniques show a positive and significant correlation with the happiness index ($r = 0.368$, $p = 0.015$), also resulting in the rejection of (H_0).

In contrast, the Punitive Disciplinary Techniques demonstrate a weak and statistically insignificant negative correlation with the happiness index ($r = -0.166$, $p = 0.288$), leading to the retention of the null hypothesis (H_0).

Table 6
Model Summary for the Regression Predicting Overall Happiness Index of the Teachers

<i>R</i> ²	Adj. <i>R</i> ²	<i>df</i> (Model)	<i>df</i> (Residual)	<i>F</i>	<i>p</i>	Significance	Inference
0.316	0.263	3	39	6.01	0.002	Significant	Reject H ₀

Table 6 presents the model summary for the multiple regression predicting teachers’ overall happiness index based on three predictors: Positive Behavioral, Punitive Disciplinary, and Social-Emotional Learning Techniques. The regression model explains 31.6% of the variance in overall happiness ($R^2 = 0.316$), with an adjusted R^2 of 0.263. The F-statistic is 6.01 with degrees of freedom (3, 39), and the model is statistically significant ($p = 0.002$).

These results indicate that the combination of the three classroom management techniques significantly predicts teachers' overall happiness index. The significant F-test suggests that the regression model provides a better fit to the data than a model without predictors.

Table 7
Multiple Regression Analysis of Predictors of the Overall Happiness Index of the Teachers

Predictors	Estimate	SE	df	t	p	Significance	Inference
(Intercept)	2.829	0.057	39	49.973	<.001	—	—
Positive Behavioral Techniques	0.546	0.203	39	2.692	0.010	Significant	Reject H ₀
Punitive Disciplinary Techniques	-0.323	0.135	39	-2.392	0.022	Significant	Reject H ₀
Social-Emotional Learning Techniques	0.163	0.176	39	0.927	0.360	Not Significant	Retain H ₀

Linear Model. $y=2.829+0.546x_1-0.323x_2+0.163x_3$

Table 7 presents the contribution of each predictor to teachers' overall happiness index. The Positive Behavioral Techniques is a significant positive predictor ($\beta = 0.546$, $p = 0.010$), while the Punitive Disciplinary Technique is a significant negative predictor ($\beta = -0.323$, $p = 0.022$). In contrast, the Social-Emotional Learning (SEL) Technique shows a positive but non-significant relationship with teacher happiness ($\beta = 0.163$, $p = 0.360$).

These results indicate that teachers who frequently implement positive behavioral strategies tend to report higher levels of happiness, whereas greater reliance on punitive disciplinary approaches is associated with lower levels of teacher well-being. Although the SEL techniques show a positive coefficient, it does not significantly predict teacher happiness within this sample.

4. Classroom Management Challenges Teachers Face

In the study, eight major themes were identified: (1) Student Behavior and Discipline; (2) Student Attention Span and Focus; (3) Student Motivation and Participation; (4) Classroom Size and Overcrowding; (5) Differentiated Instruction and Diverse Learning Needs; (6) Time Management; (7) Technology and Distractions; and (8) Group Dynamics and Cooperation. These themes emerged from recurring issues and sentiments raised by respondents from various schools, as supported by verbatim statements from the data.

Theme 1: Student Behavior and Discipline

A recurring theme among participants was the difficulty of managing student misbehavior and maintaining classroom discipline. Teachers described disruptive behaviors such as

disrespect, defiance, talking back, and disregard for classroom rules. One participant stated, “Noisy and hardheaded students,” while another remarked that “Students in this generation tend to feel superior to their teachers.” Several respondents also noted that behavioral issues are sometimes rooted in students’ home environments. For instance, one teacher explained that some students are “not disciplined at home,” which complicates classroom management.

Teachers described using various strategies to address behavioral concerns. Many emphasized personal dialogue and individual conferences, allowing students to reflect on their actions. One respondent stated, “I talk to them personally after our session,” while another said, “I give them advice and let them realize their mistakes.” Teachers also highlighted the use of clear routines, consistent rules, and positive reinforcement to maintain classroom order. In more serious cases, some teachers reported referring students to the guidance office or disciplinary officers in accordance with school policies.

Theme 2: Student Attention Span and Focus

Participants reported that students’ short attention span is a significant classroom challenge. Many teachers observed that students quickly lose focus during extended lectures or discussions. One teacher noted, “The short span of attention of the students nowadays, especially during lecture time.” Others attributed this issue to the characteristics of 21st-century learners, who are accustomed to fast-paced digital environments.

To address this challenge, teachers reported using interactive and varied teaching strategies to maintain student engagement. Some respondents emphasized incorporating student-centered activities, breaking complex lessons into manageable steps, and using real-life examples. Positive reinforcement and relationship-building were also identified as helpful strategies for sustaining attention and engagement during lessons.

Theme 3: Student Motivation and Participation

Another frequently mentioned challenge was low student motivation and participation. Teachers described encountering students who are passive, disengaged, or reluctant to participate in classroom activities. One participant shared, “A challenge I often face is getting all students to participate. Some tend to disengage or lose interest quickly.” Another teacher reported difficulty handling students who “lack motivation and avoid doing their work.”

Teachers attempted to address this issue through encouragement, group activities, and personalized engagement. Several respondents reported calling on quiet students during discussions or asking for their opinions to encourage participation. Others used small achievable goals and recognition of student progress to increase motivation and help students build confidence.

Theme 4: Classroom Size and Overcrowding

Many teachers identified large class sizes and overcrowded classrooms as significant challenges affecting classroom management and instructional effectiveness. One participant commented that “there should ideally be a maximum of 30 students per class,” explaining that larger classes make it difficult to maintain discipline and provide individual support.

Teachers noted that overcrowded classrooms often become noisy and chaotic, making it difficult to sustain attention and manage behavior. Some respondents described feeling exhausted from constantly attempting to control the class. Despite these difficulties, teachers reported coping by establishing clear rules, maintaining consistency, and building positive relationships with students to maintain order.

Theme 5: Differentiated Instruction and Diverse Learning Needs

Teachers also highlighted challenges associated with diverse learning needs and varying academic abilities within the classroom. One respondent described having “a highly diverse set of students,” while another noted the difficulty of teaching learners with special educational needs (LSEs) within mainstream classes.

To address these differences, teachers reported using individualized activities, modified tasks, and differentiated instruction strategies. Respondents emphasized the need to adapt lessons and provide additional support to ensure that all students could participate meaningfully in classroom learning.

Theme 6: Time Management

Time management emerged as another major concern among teacher respondents. Many participants reported difficulty completing planned lessons due to classroom disruptions, shortened class periods, and administrative responsibilities. One teacher explained that when time runs short, lessons often become rushed, which can negatively affect both teaching quality and student engagement.

Teachers also mentioned that frequent student absences and unexpected school activities further disrupt lesson pacing. To cope with these challenges, some teachers assign self-paced activities, combine related lessons, or continue unfinished tasks during subsequent class sessions.

Theme 7: Technology and Distractions

Teachers reported that mobile phones and digital devices are a growing source of distraction in classrooms. One participant noted that students frequently use their phones during lessons, which “affects focus and learning time.” Managing these distractions can be challenging, especially when students attempt to conceal their phone use.

To address this issue, teachers reported implementing clear classroom policies on phone use and increasing monitoring during class. Others emphasized the importance of creating engaging lessons and active learning tasks to reduce boredom and discourage off-task behavior.

Theme 8: Group Dynamics and Cooperation

Finally, teachers reported difficulties with group dynamics and student cooperation during collaborative activities. Some respondents noted that certain students do not actively contribute to group tasks, which leads to uneven participation and reduced productivity. One teacher explained that some students “do not cooperate well,” resulting in off-task behavior and increased classroom noise.

To address this issue, teachers described implementing structured group roles, close monitoring, and immediate feedback to ensure accountability. Others emphasized the importance of communication with parents, advisers, and guidance counselors when group conflicts or behavioral issues persist.

5. Integrated Faculty Development Program

Program Overview:

The proposed Integrated Faculty Development Program is designed to boost teachers' happiness and equip them with innovative classroom management skills. This program incorporates mindfulness, peer collaboration, and experiential learning into the professional development framework, creating a holistic approach to teacher support.

More importantly, the program adopts a preventive and sustainability-oriented framework. Rather than responding only to existing classroom problems, the IFDP is structured to proactively strengthen teachers' emotional resilience, instructional competence, and collaborative capacity before challenges escalate into burnout, disciplinary crises, or instructional inefficiencies.

By embedding continuous training sessions, peer mentoring structures, and recurring wellness initiatives throughout the school year, the program ensures that professional growth is not a one-time intervention but an ongoing developmental process. This long-term approach supports institutional stability, promotes consistent classroom practices, and sustains teacher well-being over time.

Objectives:

1. Increase Teacher Happiness: Promote mental and emotional well-being through stress reduction techniques, fostering a positive school culture, and encouraging a work-life balance.
2. This objective emphasizes early stress management, emotional regulation training, and regular wellness reinforcement activities to prevent emotional exhaustion and

long-term burnout. By prioritizing preventive care, the program aims to sustain teachers' psychological well-being across the academic year.

3. Enhance Classroom Management Skills: Provide innovative classroom management strategies that align with modern pedagogical practices.
4. Through structured workshops, simulations, and mentoring, this objective focuses on equipping teachers with proactive behavior management, restorative practices, and engagement strategies that prevent recurring disciplinary issues and reduce reliance on reactive measures.
5. Create a Collaborative and Supportive Environment: Build a peer support network to share experiences, challenges, and solutions, fostering a strong sense of community among educators.
6. The establishment of Peer Support Circles ensures sustained collegial dialogue, shared accountability, and continuous problem-solving. This collaborative mechanism strengthens professional relationships and institutionalizes mutual support as a long-term preventive structure against professional isolation and stress.
7. Empower Teachers Through Professional Development: Equip teachers with new, research-backed tools and approaches for effective classroom management, while keeping their well-being a priority.
8. By integrating evidence-based practices with regular monitoring, reflection logs, coaching sessions, and post-implementation evaluation, the program ensures that acquired skills are reinforced, assessed, and institutionalized. This sustainability model supports continuous improvement and long-term impact rather than short-lived training outcomes.

In general, the Integrated Faculty Development Program is intentionally designed as a preventive, continuous, and institutionally embedded initiative. By combining wellness, instructional innovation, peer collaboration, and systematic evaluation, the program promotes enduring professional growth, sustained teacher happiness, and stable classroom environments beyond a single academic cycle.

DISCUSSION

1. Classroom Management Techniques of the Teachers in terms of:

1.1 Positive Behavioral Techniques

The findings indicate that teachers demonstrate a very strong implementation of positive behavior techniques in classroom management. The frequent use of praise, rewards, and recognition suggests that teachers promote desirable student behavior through reinforcement strategies. This approach helps create a supportive classroom environment where appropriate behavior is acknowledged and encouraged, reflecting a proactive strategy that prioritizes motivation rather than punishment.

Despite the overall very high level of implementation, the slightly lower rating for the balanced use of praise and rewards suggests that some teachers may still be refining

how reinforcement is delivered. Effective reinforcement requires careful timing and moderation to ensure that praise remains meaningful and impactful. Previous studies emphasize that positive behavior support strategies improve student engagement and academic performance by reinforcing desirable behaviors (Chow et al., 2023). Providing teachers with additional training on strategic reinforcement may help strengthen the consistency and effectiveness of these practices.

These findings also support Anne Frenzel's Reciprocal Model of Teacher Emotions, which highlights the mutual influence between teacher emotions and student behavior. By reinforcing positive student actions, teachers encourage a productive classroom atmosphere, which in turn contributes to more positive emotional experiences for teachers and stronger teacher–student relationships.

1.2 Punitive Disciplinary Techniques

The findings suggest that teachers only occasionally employ punitive disciplinary techniques in classroom management, indicating that such strategies are not the primary approach to addressing student behavior. The moderate level of implementation suggests that disciplinary actions such as office referrals or raised voices are typically used when other interventions are ineffective. The low rating for over-punishing minor infractions further indicates that teachers demonstrate restraint and attempt to avoid disproportionate disciplinary responses.

These results reflect a balanced approach to discipline in which teachers appear to prioritize supportive and positive behavioral strategies before resorting to punitive measures. However, the relatively higher use of office referrals may indicate a reliance on administrative intervention when managing persistent behavioral issues. Previous research has shown that excessive punitive discipline can lead to negative student outcomes, including increased behavioral problems and reduced academic achievement (Grasley-Boy et al., 2021). In contrast, professional development programs focusing on classroom-based behavior management have been shown to strengthen teachers' skills and reduce reliance on exclusionary practices (Allen et al., 2021).

The findings also align with Anne Frenzel's Reciprocal Model of Teacher Emotions, which emphasizes the dynamic relationship between teacher emotions and student behavior. When teachers manage discipline with fairness and restraint, they help maintain a stable classroom environment that promotes positive student behavior. This interaction contributes to improved teacher well-being and more constructive teacher–student relationships.

1.3 Social-Emotional Learning Techniques

The findings indicate that teachers strongly integrate social-emotional learning (SEL) techniques into their classroom management practices. The consistently very high ratings across indicators suggest that teachers actively promote emotional awareness,

empathy, self-control, and collaborative decision-making among students. Such practices reflect a holistic approach to classroom management that prioritizes not only behavioral regulation but also the development of students' interpersonal and emotional competencies.

However, the comparatively lower mean for students' sense of responsibility suggests that while relational competencies such as empathy and perspective-taking are strongly emphasized, accountability-building practices may require further reinforcement. Research shows that SEL contributes to improved academic performance, stronger social behavior, and reduced emotional distress among students (Mahoney et al., 2021). Strengthening responsibility and self-regulation alongside empathy may therefore enhance the overall effectiveness and balance of SEL implementation.

These findings also support Anne Frenzel's Reciprocal Model of Teacher Emotions, which highlights the dynamic relationship between teacher emotions and student behavior. By fostering emotional awareness and positive social interactions, teachers create supportive classroom environments that encourage constructive student behavior. This positive interaction can enhance teachers' emotional well-being and contribute to a more harmonious and engaging learning atmosphere.

2. Perceived Level of Happiness at Work of Teachers

The findings indicate that teachers experience a very high level of happiness at work, characterized by strong enthusiasm, engagement, and a sense of belonging within their organizations. High ratings in affective commitment and work engagement suggest that teachers derive substantial intrinsic satisfaction from their professional roles. Such positive emotional experiences are important, as teacher well-being has been associated with improved job performance, retention, and a more positive school climate.

Despite the overall high level of workplace happiness, the comparatively lower score for pay satisfaction suggests a minor disparity between intrinsic motivation and extrinsic rewards. While compensation does not appear to significantly diminish overall happiness, it may still influence teachers' long-term perceptions of job satisfaction. Research indicates that supportive leadership, recognition systems, and opportunities for professional growth can enhance teacher satisfaction and motivation even in contexts where financial incentives are limited (Glaveli et al., 2023; Peláez-Fernández et al., 2021).

These results are also consistent with Bandura's Self-Efficacy Theory, which posits that individuals' confidence in their abilities influences their motivation, performance, and emotional well-being. Teachers who perceive themselves as effective and valued within their organizations are more likely to experience higher levels of engagement and satisfaction, contributing to the supportive and fulfilling work environment reflected in the findings.

3. Correlation Between the Classroom Management Styles of Teachers and their Happiness Index

The findings indicate that teachers who frequently employ Positive Behavioral and Social Emotional Learning (SEL) techniques tend to report higher levels of happiness at work. These approaches emphasize encouragement, empathy, and supportive interactions, which contribute to a more positive classroom climate and enhance teachers' sense of professional fulfillment. Previous research has shown that emotionally supportive practices and positive reinforcement strategies promote teacher well-being and engagement in the classroom (Wood et al., 2024).

Similarly, the significant relationship between SEL techniques and teacher happiness highlights the reciprocal benefits of fostering emotional awareness, empathy, and social skills in the classroom. When teachers cultivate these competencies among students, they often experience more cooperative classroom interactions and reduced behavioral challenges. Studies have found that teachers who implement SEL practices report lower burnout and higher job satisfaction (Lovett et al., 2024).

In contrast, the lack of a significant relationship between punitive disciplinary techniques and teacher happiness suggests that reliance on punitive strategies does not contribute positively to teachers' well-being. Research indicates that punitive environments may increase teacher stress and reduce morale (Hirshberg et al., 2024). Taken together, these findings emphasize that supportive classroom management strategies are more closely associated with teacher well-being than punitive approaches.

To further examine the combined influence of classroom management techniques on teacher happiness, regression analysis was conducted. The findings indicate that classroom management techniques collectively play a meaningful role in predicting teachers' happiness at work. The regression model explains approximately one-third of the variance in teachers' happiness index, indicating that classroom management practices constitute a substantial factor in shaping teachers' professional well-being.

The results highlight the importance of promoting positive behavioral and social-emotional techniques in classroom management, as these strategies can foster supportive classroom environments that benefit both students and teachers. Effective classroom management not only supports positive student behavior but also strengthens teachers' sense of accomplishment, engagement, and job satisfaction.

However, a substantial portion of the variance in teacher happiness remains unexplained, indicating that other factors may also influence teachers' well-being. Future research may therefore consider additional variables such as workload, collegial support, leadership practices, and professional development opportunities to provide a more comprehensive understanding of the determinants of teacher happiness.

Further analysis of the regression coefficients clarifies the individual contribution of each classroom management technique. The findings highlight the important role of classroom management techniques in influencing teachers' well-being. The significant positive effect

of the Positive Behavioral Techniques suggests that strategies centered on encouragement, praise, and reinforcement not only promote positive student behavior but also contribute to teachers' professional satisfaction and emotional well-being.

Conversely, the Punitive Disciplinary Techniques show a significant negative relationship with teacher happiness, indicating that reliance on punitive strategies may increase stress and reduce overall job satisfaction. This reinforces the growing emphasis on proactive and supportive discipline practices rather than reactive punitive measures.

Although Social-Emotional Learning (SEL) techniques did not significantly predict teacher happiness, the positive coefficient suggests potential benefits that may emerge with stronger implementation or in different educational contexts. Future research may further examine how factors such as SEL training, implementation fidelity, and teacher preparedness influence the relationship between SEL practices and teacher well-being to better understand how SEL initiatives may indirectly support teacher happiness.

4. Classroom Management Challenges Teachers Face

The findings of this study highlight the complex and multifaceted nature of classroom management challenges experienced by secondary school teachers. The emergence of eight key themes, student behavior and discipline, attention span, motivation and participation, classroom overcrowding, differentiated instruction, time management, technology distractions, and group dynamics, reflects the dynamic classroom conditions teachers must navigate to maintain effective learning environments.

Student behavioral issues emerged as one of the most prominent concerns among teachers. These findings align with the report of Mirmina (2025), which noted a rise in behavioral challenges in schools following the COVID-19 pandemic. Teachers' reliance on dialogue, positive reinforcement, and structured routines demonstrates their attempt to maintain discipline while preserving positive teacher–student relationships.

Another significant challenge identified was students' declining attention span. This finding supports Goldman's (2024) report that a majority of school leaders observed decreased student focus and increased classroom distractions. Teachers' responses indicate that interactive teaching strategies and varied activities are commonly used to maintain engagement, suggesting the importance of adaptive instructional practices in modern classrooms.

Low student motivation and participation also emerged as a recurring concern. These findings are consistent with Guerrero et al. (2024), who reported that integrating technology-based engagement strategies can enhance student motivation and classroom participation. Teachers in the present study similarly emphasized the importance of interactive activities, encouragement, and meaningful learning tasks to foster student involvement.

Structural classroom conditions also contribute to management challenges. The issue of overcrowded classrooms reported by participants supports the findings of Bano et al. (2025), who highlighted how large class sizes increase teacher stress and reduce

instructional effectiveness. Similarly, the difficulties teachers face in accommodating diverse learning needs reflect the conclusions of Ardenlid et al. (2025), who emphasized the importance of differentiated instruction for inclusive education.

Time constraints and competing responsibilities were also evident in teachers' experiences. These results corroborate the study of Khan et al. (2020), which found that poor time management and workload pressures contribute to teacher stress and emotional exhaustion. In addition, the growing presence of mobile phones and digital distractions mirrors the findings of Park et al. (2025), who demonstrated that structured classroom strategies can help reduce technology-related distractions.

Finally, the challenges associated with group collaboration and student cooperation align with the research of Dew et al. (2024), which highlighted how group roles, expectations, and task structures significantly influence student participation and accountability during collaborative learning. Together, these findings emphasize that classroom management is not limited to discipline alone but involves addressing behavioral, instructional, and environmental factors that influence teaching and learning.

5. Integrated Faculty Development Program

The findings of the study indicate that although teachers generally report high levels of happiness and strong implementation of positive behavioral and social-emotional learning (SEL) techniques, significant classroom management challenges persist. Issues such as student misbehavior, limited attention span, low motivation, overcrowded classrooms, diverse learning needs, time constraints, technology distractions, and group dynamics continue to affect instructional effectiveness. Moreover, the results show that while positive behavioral techniques significantly enhance teacher happiness, reliance on punitive disciplinary techniques is associated with lower well-being. These patterns highlight the need for sustained professional support that strengthens positive practices while addressing existing gaps in classroom management and teacher well-being.

In response to these identified needs, the Integrated Faculty Development Program (IFDP) was developed as a structured and preventive intervention to enhance teachers' happiness, instructional competence, and collaborative capacity. By integrating mindfulness training, peer collaboration, experiential workshops, and continuous professional development, the program directly addresses the challenges revealed in the findings. The IFDP is therefore designed not only to respond to current concerns but also to promote long-term teacher well-being, consistent classroom practices, and sustainable professional growth.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

Teachers demonstrate a strong preference for positive and supportive management approaches in their classrooms. Their emphasis on encouragement, empathy, and student engagement reflects a commitment to fostering a conducive and emotionally safe

learning environment. The minimal use of punitive strategies further indicates that teachers value constructive discipline over corrective punishment in promoting desirable student behavior.

In addition, teachers generally experience a very high level of happiness and professional satisfaction. Their enthusiasm, emotional involvement, and sense of belonging signify that they derive fulfillment from their work and institutional affiliations. However, aspects related to compensation appear to affect their overall contentment moderately.

Furthermore, teachers who consistently employ positive behavioral and social-emotional learning techniques experience greater levels of happiness and job satisfaction. These management styles contribute to a supportive and harmonious classroom climate that enhances teacher well-being. On the other hand, punitive disciplinary practices do not appear to foster the same level of professional happiness.

Moreover, managing student behavior remains the most significant classroom challenge faced by teachers. Issues such as lack of discipline, low motivation, overcrowding, and time management difficulties contribute to the complexity of classroom instruction. Despite these challenges, teachers continue to exhibit adaptability and perseverance in maintaining effective learning environments.

Recommendations

In light of the findings and conclusions, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. For Teachers: They are encouraged to sustain and further refine their implementation of positive behavioral and social-emotional learning (SEL) strategies by continuously engaging in reflective practice, peer collaboration, and structured professional development to strengthen balanced reinforcement, student accountability, and classroom consistency. By intentionally enhancing instructional strategies and emotional regulation skills, teachers can prevent recurring behavioral challenges, maintain a supportive learning environment, and promote both student success and their own professional well-being.
2. For School Administrators: School administrators are urged to translate the findings into institutional policies by strengthening evidence-based professional development programs focused on preventive classroom management, SEL integration, restorative practices, workload balance, and digital distraction management. They should also review and improve policies related to teacher recognition, compensation structures, and faculty support systems, including the formal integration of the Integrated Faculty Development Program (IFDP) into long-term school improvement and strategic planning to ensure sustainability.
3. For Policymakers: Policymakers should incorporate teacher well-being, preventive classroom management, and professional development frameworks into broader educational policies, ensuring strategic funding for manageable class sizes,

continuous capacity-building programs, inclusive education training, and accessible mental health support systems. By prioritizing proactive and evidence-based policy measures over reactive disciplinary reforms, decision-makers can strengthen teacher retention, improve school climate, and enhance overall system effectiveness.

4. For Future Researchers: It is recommended to conduct studies across diverse educational levels, institutional contexts, and cultural settings using longitudinal and mixed-methods designs to further examine the sustained impact of faculty development initiatives on teacher happiness, instructional effectiveness, and student outcomes. Additional research should also explore policy-related variables, such as the relationship between teacher well-being, retention rates, and institutional performance indicators, to provide stronger empirical evidence for data-driven educational decision-making.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study strictly adhered to established ethical research standards. Prior to participation, respondents were fully informed of the study's purpose, the voluntary nature of their involvement, their right to withdraw at any time without penalty, and the manner in which their data would be used. Informed consent was obtained from all participants before the administration of the questionnaires. Confidentiality and anonymity were upheld by refraining from collecting names or any personally identifiable information. All data were stored securely in a protected digital environment, accessible only to the researcher, thereby ensuring protection against unauthorized access and compliance with Data Privacy principles. The researchers promoted inclusivity by offering equal opportunities for participation to all high school teachers, regardless of gender, socioeconomic background, or academic discipline. The questionnaire posed no known risks to participants, and efforts were made to minimize any potential discomfort, thereby safeguarding the well-being of the respondents throughout the study.

Ethical integrity was maintained throughout the research process, including transparency in data collection, analysis, and reporting of findings. The researcher ensured that there was no bias in the interpretation of the results and that the findings were used purely for academic and research purposes, particularly in improving teachers' classroom management techniques and enhancing their happiness index. Furthermore, no conflict of interest existed in the conduct of the study, and all sources of information used in the research were properly acknowledged to strictly avoid plagiarism.

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